

1. Evaluator Information

Name: _____

Academic Background: _____

Area of Expertise: _____

Years of Experience in the Field: _____

2. Checklist Evaluation

We kindly request your collaboration in evaluating three checklists developed within the context of a research study on change management in software development projects. The aim of the study was to understand the main impacts of changes in this type of project. Based on results obtained through a systematic literature review and a survey with professionals in the field, practical tools were developed to support the following:

- Assessment of maturity in project scope definition
- Validation of function and non-functional requirements
- Support for managing change requests throughout the project life cycle

Your participation is essential to validate the clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of the proposed items, directly contributing to the rigor and applicability of the research. Your critical analysis will be extremely valuable for improving both the study and the instruments.

Please evaluate each checklist item based on the following criteria:

- **Clarity** – Is the item written in an understandable way?
- **Relevance** – Is the item important for the checklist's objective?
- **Adequacy** – Is the item properly formulated for its intended purpose?

Scope Definition					
ID	Checklist Item	Clarity Is the item written in an understandable way?	Relevance Is the item important for the checklist's objective?	Adequacy Is the item properly formulated for its intended purpose?	Comments / Additional Suggestions
1	Is the main deliverable clearly defined, including objectives and core functionalities?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
2	Are out-of-scope elements identified to avoid ambiguity?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
3	Have the stakeholders and end-users been identified, and are their needs considered?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
4	Are the expected benefits (economic, operational, or strategic) clearly stated?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
5	Have all technical, legal, operational, financial, and timeline constraints been identified?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
6	Are system integrations and required interfaces specified or planned?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
7	Does the scope include performance, reliability, or other critical quality requirements?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
8	Has the scope's technical, operational, and economic feasibility been evaluated by the team?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	

9	Is the scope aligned with business goals and validated by stakeholders?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
10	Are there measurable criteria to define project success and acceptance?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	

Requirements Gathering					
ID	Checklist Item	Clarity Is the item written in an understandable way?	Relevance Is the item important for the checklist's objective?	Adequacy Is the item properly formulated for its intended purpose?	Comments / Additional Suggestions
1	Is the requirement written clearly and unambiguously?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
2	Is the requirement understandable by all stakeholders and the technical team?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
3	Is the requirement realistic in relation to current technology and within the project scope?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
4	Does the requirement avoid anticipating implementation decisions (premature design)?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
5	Is the requirement testable (can it be verified through testing or validation)?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
6	Is the requirement necessary and does it meet	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree	

	the real need of the stakeholders?	<input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
7	Is the requirement traceable to its business objective or origin?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
8	Does the requirement have flexibility for changes, if necessary?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
9	Is the requirement accepted by all involved stakeholders?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
10	Does the requirement directly contribute to the project or product objectives?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	

Change Management					
ID	Checklist Item	Clarity Is the item written in an understandable way?	Relevance Is the item important for the checklist's objective?	Adequacy Is the item properly formulated for its intended purpose?	Comments / Additional Suggestions
1	Is the request a real change or a specific customization?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
2	Does the change refer to a Functional Requirement (RF) or a Non-Functional Requirement (NFR)?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
3	Does the change impact existing requirements (scope, deliverables, or previous versions)?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	

4	Is there a direct impact on the schedule, cost, or team effort?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
5	Will the change result in significant rework? If so, has it been assessed?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
6	Has a technical impact and feasibility analysis been conducted?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
7	Was the change discussed with the PO and/or Project Manager before the final decision?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
8	Was the change recorded and prioritized in the backlog once accepted?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
9	Does the change benefit more than one client or stakeholder, or bring collective value?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	
10	Was there resistance to change? If so, was it discussed and justified?	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/> Strongly disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially disagree <input type="radio"/> Partially agree <input type="radio"/> Strongly agree	

3. General Comments

Please use the space below to record any criticisms, general suggestions, missing items, or relevant observations: